

The Role of the Personality of the Teacher in the Educational Process

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Abstract: This article describes the personal qualities of the teacher as a factor affecting the educational process of students, the requirements for these qualities. The main characteristics of the teacher are noted. The professional orientation of the teacher, what it is and what it includes is revealed.

Keywords: personal qualities of the teacher; professional orientation; educational process

Introduction

In the educational process, it is impossible not to single out such a powerful pedagogical factor as the nature of the educator, the properties and qualities of his personality. Teachers differ in character, willpower, temperament, style of communication. The direct expression of irascibility, cruelty, spinelessness speaks of the teacher's poor knowledge of psychology and pedagogy, the evasion of forming one's character and overcoming oneself. The pedagogical authority of the individual determines the acceptable form of expression and development of discipline and democracy in education.

Relevance

Pedagogical activity is the type of activity, the result of which is influenced by the nature of the relationship between its participants. The successful solution of complex and decisive tasks of teaching and educating children depends on the moral position, professional skills, culture, personality of the teacher. Correction by a teacher of personal and professional qualities can significantly improve the level of education, and therefore lead to an improvement in the educational activities of schoolchildren.

Target: To study the features of the influence of the personality of the teacher on the educational process.

Tasks:

- to reveal the term "educational process" on the basis of a theoretical analysis of the literature;
- to determine the actual qualities of the personality of the teacher, influencing the educational process;
- to reveal the role of diagnostics in the educational process and to establish its influence on the success of pedagogical activity.

Research materials: analysis of literary sources on the problem under study.

Research methods: analysis, synthesis, generalization.

Scientific novelty: the influence of the teacher's professional orientation on the educational process has been revealed.

The strength of the educational impact is determined by the one who conducts it. The role of the teacher's personality is the most important factor influencing the effectiveness of the educational process. Special requirements for the personality of a teacher are imposed by the social significance of pedagogical activity. K.D. Ushinsky noted that the personality of a teacher is a fruitful ray of the sun irreplaceable by anything, indeed, it is difficult to disagree with these words.

To date, there has been a sharp increase in interest in the personality of the teacher, namely, in his skill, professionalism, and individual psychological characteristics. These requirements, it is difficult to say that this is just an interest, they are connected with the fact that the educational process is directly related to the personality of the teacher. The position of a teacher is not just a profession, but work to create a person's personality.

The basis of pedagogical duty is love for children. This is a fundamental quality, a prerequisite for self-improvement. An additional, but relatively stable requirement is sociability, goodwill, intelligence, emotional-volitional qualities, and others.

“Any educational work should begin with the fact that the teacher learns, realizes the educational functions ...”, so B.D. Ulugov stated [1, 2]. In educational work, three groups of functions should be distinguished:

- 1) is associated with the influence of the teacher on the student;
- 2) is associated with the creation of an educative atmosphere;
- 3) is aimed at correcting the influence of various subjects of the child's social relations.

Before defining the connection between the educational process and the role of the teacher's personality in this process, we will reveal the concept of the educational process.

We can consider the educational process as an integral dynamic system, the system formation factor of which is the goal of developing the personality of the educated person, realized in the interaction of the teacher and the student. The educational process is an integral core of the pedagogical activity of an educational institution, where pedagogical activity is the activity of adult members of society, whose professional goal is to educate the younger generation [3, 4].

In the Kuzmina N.V. an approach that suggested considering personality as the ability of an individual “to cause changes in significant aspects of other people’s individuality through their representation in them” [7]. Indeed, we reflect the behavior of that the person we are surrounded by. And students, all the more so, they are the younger generation, and while they have not yet developed their own clear character, they will form it by copying. Students spend most of their time at school surrounded by the teaching staff, and the role of the teacher's personality plays an important role here [5, 6]. It is the personality of the teacher that influences the success of pedagogical activity, and one or another of his properties will increase or decrease the educational influence.

To continuously improve the level of the educational process and to meet professional needs, diagnostics of pedagogical activity is carried out. (Diagnosis of the professional position of the teacher as an educator (self-assessment)). It also allows you to recognize the main professional and personal characteristics of the teacher testing conducted among students (Class teacher through the eyes of pupils).

We have carried out diagnostics of teachers, whose students had average and low discipline in the classroom. For the experiment, two teachers who were facing problems in the class proposed their initiative. Based on the results obtained, it was revealed that the manifestation of such

discipline is associated to a greater extent with the personality of the teacher. The teachers revealed their mistakes and made recommendations for self-correction and self-knowledge.

Testing was also conducted among students in the same classes, and many answered the question “Do you have trouble at school and from whom do they leave?” noted teachers and to the question “Do you have conflicts with a teacher?” gave a positive answer.

Conclusion

Thus, one of the most important factors influencing the process of education is the personality of the teacher. The teaching profession refers to a group of professions whose subject is a person.

Each teacher should strive for brightness, emotionality, sociability, intelligence, a variety of types of work, meaningfulness of classes. Each teacher must understand the importance of the role of his personality in the educational process of each child.

The problem of diagnosing the pedagogical activity of teachers is extremely relevant, it is of great importance both for improving the educational process and for raising the level of teachers' qualifications. The main value of diagnostics is that it helps to identify shortcomings and outline specific ways to solve them.

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**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O‘RTA MAXSUS
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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2021-yil 3-dekabrda PQ-30-son "Termiz muhandislik-texnologiya instituti faoliyatini tashkil etish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi qarorida ilmiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish, ilmiy ishlarning natijadorligini ta'minlash, professor-o'qituvchilar va xodimlarni ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlariga faol jalb etish, Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar kabi xalqaro ma'lumotlar bazalarida ilmiy maqolalarni chop etish va iqtiboslik darajasini oshirish, amaliy, fundamental va innovatsion tadqiqotlar mavzularini hududiy va ishlab chiqarish sohalari muammolarini hisobga olgan holda qayta ko'rib chiqish, xorijiy mamlakatlarda o'tkaziladigan xalqaro konferensiyalar, simpoziumlar va seminarlarda muntazam ravishda ishtirokini ta'minlash" belgilab q'yilgan.

Faoliyatini boshlaganiga besh yil bo'lgan institutimizda 170 dan ortiq professor-o'qituvchilar 70 nafar magistrant va 5722 nafar talabalarga tahsil berish bilan birgalikda ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlarida ustoz shogird tizimi tashkil qilingan hamda yuqori natijalarga erishib kelmoqda.

Institut miqyosida tashkil etilayotgan anjuman o'z oldiga iqtidorli yoshlarni tanlash, ularga shart-sharoit yaratish, ilmiy izlanishlarga keng jalb etish maqsad qilib qo'ygan. Shu bilan birgalikda institutda muhandis-texnolog kadrlar tayyorlanishini hisobga olgan holda eng yaxshi innovatsion loyihalarni moliyalashtirish, iqtidorli ixtirochi, injener-konstruktor, dasturchi, rasionalizatorlarni tanlash hamda keyingi bosqichga yo'naltirish anjumanning asosiy maqsadi hisoblanadi.

Texnika va texnologiya yo'nalishlarida olib borilayotgan ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlar, zamonaviy texnologiyalar, fan sohasidagi muammo va yechimlarni muhokama qilishga bag'ishlangan anjuman tarmoqning yanada rivoji uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Anjumanda ishtirok etgan xorijiy mutaxassislariga alohida minnatdorchilik bildirgan holda ularni tegishli sohalar bo'yicha o'zaro manfaatli hamkorlik aloqalariga chorlab qolamiz.

O'ylanmanki, institutimizda o'tkazilayotgan anjuman ilmiy izlanishlardagi mavjud muammolarni aniqlash hamda ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarini amaliyotga joriy etish bilan birgalikda yoshlarning iqtidorini namoyon etish imkoniyatini yaratadi. Eng asosiysi institut rahbariyatining kelgusidagi talaba yoshlar va yosh o'qituvchilarning ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlarini tashkil etishda muhim yo'nalishlarni belgilab beradi.

Institut rahbari sifatida shuni ta'kidlab o'tmoqchimanki, ushbu anjuman orqali eng kamida bir nafar talabani ilmga yo'naltira olgan bo'lsak oldimizga qo'ygan asosiy maqsadimizga erishdik deb hisoblashimiz mumkin.

Institut rektori

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Ushbu to'plamda Oliy ta'lim muassasalari va ilmiy-tadqiqot institutlarida faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan professor-o'qituvchi va talabalarning ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarining natijalari e'lon qilingan. Anjuman materiallari O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligining 2022-yil 29-sentabrdagi 3/19-4/4-2403-son xati va institut rektorining 2022-yil 20-noyabrdagi 75-U-sonli qarori asosida nashrga tavsiya etildi.

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